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**MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF STUDENTS' ENROLMENT, RETENTION AND
GRADUATION IN NIGERIAN UNIVERSITIES**

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Abstract

A mathematical model of enrolment, retention and graduation in Nigerian Universities was developed and studied for existence and uniqueness, equilibrium and stability. The analytical solution showed that the model's solution exists and is unique. It was also proved that at the interaction free equilibrium, the model equations are asymptotically stable. ODE45 of MATLAB R2015a was used to simulate the numerical solution to determine the number of student in the institutions and those that have graduated at time (t), it was discovered that the student population and the graduates of an institution can be determined by the code given any initial data using the model.

Keywords: Mathematical Model, Enrolment, Retention, Graduation

Introduction

Universities have existed for quite a long time. Although they are created to cater for the needs of the societies, arguments about their role and functions have continued to rage on (Denman, 2005). According to Simpson and Johnston (2006) "there is a fundamental tension in institutions' attitudes towards one of their other important functions – the successful production of graduates." Hunt (2006) opines that the fundamental educational challenge of our times is to get more people better educated and get most of them through postsecondary education. The effectiveness of candidates admitted into any higher institution affects the level of research and training within the institution, and by extension, affects the expectations and demands of the society, as these products eventually become key players in all sectors (Olusola, 2015). Of course, it also determines student retention or otherwise. Although there are ambivalent views on student increased retention, some researchers are of the view that increased retention in some institution can be seen as a sign of lower academic standards and thus, lower institutional status (Simpson and Johnston, 2006). They suggest that this need not be the case and that retention can be increased with no effect on standards.

Although no law makes university education mandatory in Nigeria, the premium placed on it has made it so competitive that only a fraction of those seeking admission into them get admitted. The main objective of the admission system in Nigeria is to determine candidates who would likely do well in the university. The mode of entry into universities in Nigeria are: Direct entry (DE) and through the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME). Candidates aspiring to gain admission into the first year have to pass the prescribed number of subjects at SSCE, meet the UTME cut-off mark of the institution to which they are applying and must also attend or pass Post UTME screening or test as the case may be. While for those seeking admission into the second year need to have the required 'A' Level passes, in addition to meeting the 'O' Level requirements and attend screening exercise as may be required by their prospective institutions.

According to the U.S. Department of Education, about 79 percent of first year students return to college for a subsequent year at four-year institutions, and 60 percent return to two-year institutions. This means that a substantial number of students who enter colleges and universities will not return the next year to continue with their program. (Braxton and Hirschy, 2005). If this record is anything to go by, the need for institutions to keep track of their students' progressions and of course retention cannot be overemphasized. The aim of this work is to develop a mathematical model of admission, retention and graduation of student in universities using the mode of admission into the Nigerian University system. It is also expected to be used to determine the population of students in a university at any particular session and the population of those graduated at particular time and for whatever period required.

Model Development

Most of the courses in Nigerian universities have four years as duration for studies. The mode of entry is either through the UTME into year one or through Direct entry into the second. Based on these, we propose a model of enrolment into universities with the assumption that the programs are of four years duration and that each year is a level of study where the population of the students are partitioned into five compartments $P_1(t)$, $P_2(t)$, $P_3(t)$ and $P_4(t)$ are first (part one), second (part two), third(part three) and fourth levels (part four) of study respectively and $P_5(t)$ are those who have graduated (graduates) at time (t). The population of part one grows as a result of admission Λ_1 and demotion of part two students γ_1 and loses through progression to part two α_1 and μ_1 due to dropping out of the system for whatever reason. The part two compartment grows through DE admission Λ_2 , promotion from part one α_1 , and demotions from part three γ_2 and this compartment loses through promotions to part three α_2 , demotion to part one γ_1 and μ_2 dropping out of the system. Part three receives promotions from part two α_2 , demotions from part four γ_3 and loses to part four α_3 , demotion to part two γ_2 and μ_3 dropping out of the system. The fourth part gains through promotions from part three α_3 , inability for some students to graduate γ_3 and loses through graduating α_4 , demotion to part three γ_3 and dropping out of the system μ_4 . The successfully graduating students do at the rate α_4 and those have not graduated but are supposed to graduate return

to part four γ_4 . We also assume that the students interact at the rate β and that the interactions are such that all the levels interact with the levels next to them.

Based on the assumptions and the descriptions above we present the schematic diagram of the model in the figure below.

Figure 1: Schematic Representation of the Model

Model Equations

The assumptions, descriptions and the schematic diagram in figure 1 are described by the following equations

$$\frac{dP_1}{dt} = \Lambda_1 - (\alpha_1 + \mu_1)P_1 + \gamma_1 P_2 - \beta P_1 P_2 \tag{1}$$

$$\frac{dP_2}{dt} = \Lambda_2 + \alpha_1 P_1 - (\alpha_2 + \mu_2 + \gamma_1)P_2 + \gamma_2 P_3 + \beta P_1 P_2 - \beta P_2 P_3 \tag{2}$$

$$\frac{dP_3}{dt} = \alpha_2 P_2 - (\alpha_3 + \mu_3 + \gamma_2) P_3 + \gamma_3 P_4 + \beta P_2 P_3 - \beta P_3 P_4 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dP_4}{dt} = \alpha_3 P_3 - (\alpha_4 + \mu_4 + \gamma_3) P_4 + \gamma_4 P_5 + \beta P_3 P_4 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dP_5}{dt} = \alpha_4 P_4 - \gamma_4 P_5 \quad (5)$$

$$N = P_1 + P_2 + P_3 + P_4 + P_5 \quad (6)$$

$$P_1(0) \geq 0, P_2(0) \geq 0, P_3(0) \geq 0, P_4(0) \geq 0, P_5(0) \geq 0$$

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = \Lambda_1 + \Lambda_2 - (\mu_1 + \mu_2 + \mu_3 + \mu_4) P \quad (7)$$

Existence and Uniqueness of the Solution of the Model Equations

We adopt the approach by Wangercha et al. (2022), to determine the existence and uniqueness of the equations of the model.

Theorem 1: Picard’s Theorem

Suppose $f(t, x)$ is continuous and satisfies a Lipchitz condition in the closed and bounded domain

$\|x - x_0\| \leq \varphi, \|t - t_0\| \leq \tau$, then any equation of the form

$$x'(t) = f(t, x(t)), \quad x(t_0) = x_0 \quad (8)$$

called an initial value problem has a unique solution in the interval $\|t - t_0\| \leq h$

where $h = \left\{ \tau, \frac{\varphi}{M} \right\}$.

The model equations will be transformed into the form (8) and the theorem above will be used to prove the existence and uniqueness of the transformed equations.

Consider equations (1)-(5),

Let

$$x = [P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5]^T$$

$$f(t, x) = [f_1(t, x), f_2(t, x), f_3(t, x), f_4(t, x), f_5(t, x)]^T \quad (9)$$

Where

$$f_1(t, x) = \Lambda_1 - (\alpha_1 + \mu_1)P_1 + \gamma_1 P_2 - \beta P_1 P_2$$

$$f_2(t, x) = \Lambda_2 + \alpha_1 P_1 - (\alpha_2 + \mu_2 + \gamma_1)P_2 + \gamma_2 P_3 + \beta P_1 P_2 - \beta P_2 P_3$$

$$f_3(t, x) = \alpha_2 P_2 - (\alpha_3 + \mu_3 + \gamma_2)P_3 + \gamma_3 P_4 + \beta P_2 P_3 - \beta P_3 P_4 \quad (10)$$

$$f_4(t, x) = \alpha_3 P_3 - (\alpha_4 + \mu_4 + \gamma_3)P_4 + \gamma_4 P_5 + \beta P_3 P_4$$

$$f_5(t, x) = \alpha_4 P_4 - \gamma_4 P_5$$

The model equations are now of the form (8).

Suppose the function $f(t, x)$ is defined and continuous in x and satisfies a Lipchitz condition in the closed and bounded region

Let

$$D = \{x = (P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5) : P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5 \leq 1\} \quad (11)$$

Define

$$\|x - x_0\| \leq \varphi, \|t\| \leq \tau, t_0 = 0, x_0 = (P_1 0, P_2 0, P_3 0, P_4 0, P_5 0)$$

We shall prove using Picard's theorem that the solution of (1)-(5) exists and is unique, by proving the following:

1. f is continuous
2. f satisfies Lipchitz condition
3. $|f| \leq M$

$f(t, x)$ is continuous since each component of $f_i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ is a continuous function of the variable $x = [P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5]^T$.

To establish the Lipchitz condition for the model equations,

$$\text{Let } x_* = [P_1^*, P_2^*, P_3^*, P_4^*, P_5^*]^T$$

$$f(x_*) = [f_1(x_*), f_2(x_*), f_3(x_*), f_4(x_*), f_5(x_*)]^T$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} |f_1(x) - f_1(x_*)| &= |\Lambda_1 - (\alpha_1 + \mu_1)P_1 + \gamma_1 P_2 + \beta P_1 P_2| \\ &= |\Lambda_1 + (-\alpha_1)(P_1 - P_1^*) + \mu_1(P_1 - P_1^*) + \gamma_1(P_2 - P_2^*) - \beta[(P_1 - P_1^*)(P_2 - P_2^*)]| \\ &\leq |\Lambda_1 + \alpha_1 + \mu_1| |P_1 - P_1^*| + \gamma_1 |P_2 - P_2^*| + \beta |P_1 - P_1^*| + \beta |P_2 - P_2^*| \\ &= (\Lambda_1 + \alpha_1 + \mu_1 + \beta) |P_1 - P_1^*| + (\beta + \gamma_1) |P_2 - P_2^*| \\ &= l_{11} |P_1 - P_1^*| + l_{12} |P_2 - P_2^*| + l_{13} |P_3 - P_3^*| + l_{14} |P_4 - P_4^*| + l_{15} |P_5 - P_5^*| \\ |f_1(x) - f_1(x_*)| &\leq L_1 \|x - x_*\| \end{aligned}$$

Where,

$$L_1 = \max \{l_{11}, l_{12}, l_{13}, l_{14}, l_{15}\}, \quad l_{11} = \Lambda_1 + \alpha_1 + \mu_1 + \beta, \quad l_{12} = \gamma_1 + \beta, \quad l_{13} = 0, \quad l_{14} = 0, \quad l_{15} = 0$$

are constants depending on the parameters of the model.

Similarly,

$$|f_2(x) - f_2(x_*)| \leq L_2 \|x - x_*\|$$

Where,

$$L_2 = \max \{l_{21}, l_{22}, l_{23}, l_{24}, l_{25}\}, \quad l_{21} = \alpha_1 + \beta, \quad l_{22} = \Lambda_2 + \alpha_2 + \mu_2 + \gamma_1, \quad l_{23} = \gamma_2 + \beta, \quad l_{24} = 0, \quad l_{25} = 0,$$

$$|f_3(x) - f_3(x_*)| \leq L_3 \|x - x_*\|$$

Where,

$$L_3 = \max\{l_{31}, l_{32}, l_{33}, l_{34}, l_{35}\}, l_{31} = 0, l_{32} = \alpha_2 + \beta, l_{33} = \alpha_3 + \mu_3 + \gamma_2 + 2\beta,$$

$$l_{34} = \gamma_3 + \beta, l_{35} = 0,$$

$$|f_4(x) - f_4(x_*)| \leq L_4 \|x - x_*\|$$

Where,

$$L_4 = \max\{l_{41}, l_{42}, l_{43}, l_{44}, l_{45}\}, l_{41} = 0, l_{42} = 0, l_{43} = \alpha_3 + \beta, l_{44} = \alpha_4 + \mu_4 + \gamma_3 + \beta, l_{45} = \gamma_4,$$

$$|f_5(x) - f_5(x_*)| \leq L_5 \|x - x_*\|$$

Where,

$$L_5 = \max\{l_{51}, l_{52}, l_{53}, l_{54}, l_{55}\}, l_{51} = 0, l_{52} = 0, l_{53} = 0, l_{54} = \alpha_4, l_{55} = \alpha_5 + \gamma_4,$$

$$\|f(x) - f(x_*)\| = \max_{1 \leq i \leq 5} \{|f_1(x) - f_1(x_*)| + \dots + |f_5(x) - f_5(x_*)|\}$$

$$= \max_{1 \leq i \leq 5} L_i \|x - x_*\|, i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$$

$$\leq L \|x - x_*\|$$

Where,

$$L = \max\{L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4, L_5\}$$

To obtain the bound for f , we have,

$$|f_1(x)| \leq \Lambda_1 + (\alpha_1 + \mu_1\beta)|P_1| + (\gamma_1 + \beta)|P_2|$$

$$= \Lambda_1 + \alpha_1 + \mu + \gamma_1 + 2\beta$$

$$= M_1$$

Similarly,

$$|f_2(x)| \leq \Lambda_2 + \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \mu_2 + \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + 4\beta$$

$$= M_2$$

$$|f_3(x)| \leq \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \mu_3 + \gamma_2 + \gamma_3 + 4\beta$$

$$= M_3$$

$$|f_4(x)| \leq \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 + \mu_4 + \gamma_3 + \gamma_4 + 2\beta$$

$$= M_4$$

$$f_5(x) \leq \alpha_4 + \gamma_4$$

$$= M_5$$

Therefore,

$$\|f(x)\| = \max\{M_1, M_2, M_3, M_4, M_5\} \\ \leq M$$

Thus, there exists a unique solution for the IVP in some interval $h = \min\left\{\tau, \frac{\varphi}{M}\right\}$.

Stability Analysis of the Model Equations

The Interaction Free Equilibrium state of the model equation E_0 , where $P_{10} \neq 0, P_{20} \neq 0, P_{30} = 0, P_{40} = 0, P_{50}$ is obtained as

Theorem 2: The Equilibrium State of (1)-(5) is Locally Asymptotically Stable if

$$\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4, \lambda_5 < 0$$

Proof:

Let,

$$F_1 = \Lambda_1 - (\alpha_1 + \mu_1)P_1 + \gamma_1P_2 - \beta P_1P_2$$

$$F_2 = \Lambda_2 + \alpha_1P_1 - (\alpha_2 + \mu_2 + \gamma_1)P_2 + \gamma_2P_3 + \beta P_1P_2 - \beta P_2P_3$$

$$F_3 = \alpha_2P_2 - (\alpha_3 + \mu_3 + \gamma_2)P_3 + \gamma_3P_4 + \beta P_2P_3 - \beta P_3P_4 \tag{12}$$

$$F_4 = \alpha_3P_3 - (\alpha_4 + \mu_4 + \gamma_3)P_4 + \gamma_4P_5 + \beta P_3P_4$$

$$F_5 = \alpha_4 P_4 - (\mu_5 + \gamma_4) P_5$$

$$J(E) = \begin{bmatrix} -(\alpha_1 + \mu_1 - \beta P_2) & \gamma_1 - \beta P_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha_1 + \beta P_2 & -(\alpha_2 + \mu_2 + \gamma_1 + \beta P_1 - \beta P_3) & \gamma_2 - \beta P_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_2 + \beta P_3 & -(\alpha_3 + \mu_3 + \gamma_2 + \beta P_2 - \beta P_4) & \gamma_3 - \beta P_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_3 + \beta P_4 & -(\alpha_4 + \mu_4 + \gamma_3 - \beta P_3 + \beta P_4) & \gamma_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha_4 & -\gamma_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

At interaction free equilibrium $\beta = 0$, (14) becomes

$$JI(0) = \begin{bmatrix} -(\alpha_1 + \mu_1) & \gamma_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha_1 & -(\alpha_2 + \mu_2 + \gamma_1) & \gamma_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_2 & -(\alpha_3 + \mu_3 + \gamma_2) & \gamma_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_3 & -(\alpha_4 + \mu_4 + \gamma_3) & \gamma_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha_4 & -\gamma_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

After some arithmetic, we have

$$= \begin{bmatrix} -A - \lambda_1 & \alpha_1 \gamma_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -B - \lambda_2 & \alpha_2 \gamma_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -C - \lambda_3 & \alpha_3 \gamma_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -D - \lambda_4 & \alpha_4 \gamma_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -E - \lambda_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

$$\lambda_1 = -A, \lambda_2 = -B, \lambda_3 = -C, \lambda_4 = -D, \lambda_5 = -E,$$

Where

$$A = \alpha_1(\alpha_1 + \mu_1)$$

$$B = \alpha_2(\alpha_1 + \mu_1)(\alpha_2 + \mu_2 + \gamma_1) + \alpha_1 \gamma_1$$

$$C = \alpha_3(\alpha_1 + \mu_1)(\alpha_2 + \mu_2 + \gamma_1)(\alpha_3 + \mu_3 + \gamma_2) + \alpha_2 \gamma_2$$

$$D = \alpha_4(\alpha_1 + \mu_1)(\alpha_2 + \mu_2 + \gamma_1)(\alpha_3 + \mu_3 + \gamma_2)(\alpha_4 + \mu_4 + \gamma_3)$$

$$E = (\alpha_5 + \mu_5 + \gamma_4)$$

$$\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4, \lambda_5 < 0. \quad \square$$

Numerical Simulations

Numerical simulations are performed on the model using ODE45 of the MATLAB software. The following hypothetical values of student population and parameters from some literatures are used for the simulations; $P_1 = 5000$, $P_2 = 5000$, $P_3 = 4000$, $P_4 = 3200$, $P_5 = 3040$ and $\Lambda_1 = 5000$; $\Lambda_2 = 1000$; $\alpha_1 = 0.8$; $\alpha_2 = 0.8$; $\alpha_3 = 0.8$; $\alpha_4 = 0.8$; $\mu_1 = 0.15$; $\mu_2 = 0.10$; $\mu_3 = 0.10$; $\mu_4 = 0.10$; $\gamma_1 = 0.05$; $\gamma_2 = 0.05$; $\gamma_3 = 0.05$; $\gamma_4 = 0.05$; $\gamma_5 = 0.05$; $\beta = 0.05$. The graphical representation of the result of the simulation is presented in figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Number of Students and Graduates after four years

Discussion of the Findings

In this work, a mathematical model of enrolment, retention and graduation in Nigerian Universities was developed and studied. We adopted the epidemic model approach to develop the model because of the similarities between the behaviours of the two populations. In the epidemic model the population is made up of those that have disease and those who do not have the disease, in this model the population is made up of those in the university and those who are out. Similarly, both have the characteristics of interaction between the various members of their populations. The following are the findings based on the analyses and the numerical simulations.

The solution of the model equations is found to exist and are unique. Similarly, they are also stable as determined. The property that a small change in the initial size x_o of a solution has only a small effect on the behaviour of the solution as $t \rightarrow \infty$ is called *stability* of the solution. We will require stability of any solution to which we ascribe significance; if a small disturbance can cause a large change in the solution it is unreasonable to

consider the solution meaningful. Hence our model equations are reasonable and can be used for the purpose of the study.

The study models the intake (admission) up to the process of graduation in the university system. Hence from the two modes of admission the progression of students, the various programmes, retention and graduation of an institution can be monitored and controlled by making use of the model to suit such purposes. This will go a long way in easing the tension suggested in Simpson and Johnston (2006) and assist in making institutions to be deliberate in their efforts in admission and retention of students. This is because, of inadequacy in the number of Universities in Nigeria coupled with the high demand for University education. These have created the problems of admissions into the available Universities and the sustenance of good standards (Okoroma, 2015).

The numerical simulation shows that the student population at any point in time can be determined. This will help in making the institution to plan their students, retention and determine the number of students that have and will graduate at any given or for any given period. The use of numerical simulation further gives the advantage of estimation of student enrolment, retention and planning. This is vital especially with the rise in number of applicants and the corresponding limited openings in the universities.

Conclusion

We developed and studied a mathematical model of enrolment, retention and graduation in Nigerian Universities. We studied the existence and uniqueness of the solution of the model equations using the approach by Wangercha et. al. (2022). We established that the solution of the model equations exists and is unique. The equations are locally asymptotically stable and numerical simulation using Matlab R2015a was used for numerical simulation. The result showed that the number of students and those who graduated in an institution can be determined using the model. The model's goal is to contribute to the solution of the problem of admission, retention and graduation in Nigeria's University system. We recommend that policy makers and implementers should adapt the model to their specific needs for improvement of admission, retention and admission not only in the universities but other institutions.

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